

Social Media and Study Habits Among Maritime Students in Davao City

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ABSTRACT

The growing role of social media in students' academic behaviors has raised concerns about its impact on study habits among maritime students. This study investigated the association between social media and study habits among Bachelor of Science in Marine Transportation (BSMT) students at DMMA College of Southern Philippines, Inc. The researchers implemented a non-experimental quantitative research design, a descriptive-correlational approach. The study was done in Davao City, Philippines, with 335 BSMT students as participants, through stratified random sampling and simple random sampling. Data were collected with a modified survey questionnaire on social media (Facebook and

Twitter/Threads) and study habits (time management, study routines, and study techniques). Data were analyzed using statistical methods, including means, standard deviations, Pearson's r , and multiple regression. The results showed that although students were engaging with social media to a moderate extent, their study habits were high. The data showed that social media also had a statistically significant positive association with study habits. Both Facebook and Twitter/Threads were also significantly impactful on students' study habits, with Facebook having a stronger predictive impact. These findings suggest that social media can positively affect student academic behaviors when used purposefully and responsibly. Thus, balanced, academically oriented social media promotes study habits. Discipline-based use of social media by students, schools encouraging the guided integration of digital platforms into learning, and additional variables and contexts can be examined by future researchers to solidify the findings.

Keywords: *Social Media, Study Habits, BSMT Students, Maritime, and Davao City*

INTRODUCTION

The need for study habits is well-documented in education, enabling consistency across high-yield learning activities such as reading, note-taking, and completing coursework (David et al., 2024). However, Muhammad et al. (2023) found that globally, many university students struggle to maintain consistent study strategies and learning habits, such as time management, and face challenges related to procrastination and poor self-discipline. Aljaffer et al. (2024) also argued that irregular study habits may reduce students' long-term commitment to studying and their engagement with academic materials. Moreover, Valdez (2025) described how poor study habits remain a prominent concern for universities and can significantly affect academic performance. Collectively, such findings underscore the importance of understanding the context

and predictors that affect students' study habits. In Spain, personal, digital, and environmental factors determine students' study habits. Students' attention during academic activities is frequently diverted by social media and online entertainment (Pérez Juárez et al., 2023). A separate transition during the COVID-19 pandemic changed routines and required greater self-discipline (Jereb et al., 2023). The persistence of procrastination, disorganization, and irregular study patterns is the most common problem confronting students in universities (Santos et al., 2022, & Ünal, 2021). As Castro (2021) suggested, these difficulties are increasingly recognized as obstacles to good, regular study.

In the Philippines, Filipino students also find it difficult to maintain focus in their studies. Many learners in the country have poor time-management and study routines, which harm their academic performance (Cuizon et al., 2022). The practice of remote and blended learning, especially for students with unreliable internet access and poor home study conditions (Balano & Napil, 2024), has challenged students' self-discipline. Moreover, high social media engagement is associated with poor focus and inconsistent study habits among Filipino students (Sacurom et al., 2025).

In Davao City, students' study habits are influenced by their characteristics and the school environment. Balano and Napil (2024) have noted that levels of emotional intelligence and the ability to adapt to the changing nature of digital learning systems affect how well students meet their academic assignments. Furthermore, high screen time might interfere with one's ability to organize study routines and manage time efficiently. Good study skills, such as effective time management strategies and reading competencies, enhance students' motivation and interest, while the inability to master them can lower academic discipline (Franca & Napil, 2022). Among other factors are the importance of study habits, the desire to improve critical thinking, and the enhancement of student academic performance at the university level in Davao Oriental (Vallejos & Edig, 2025).

Despite extensive research on study behavior, few studies examine the effects of social media on students' study habits, especially among maritime students in the Philippines (Van Tuan, 2021). Moreover, other research indicates that social media engagement influences students' study schedules and learning styles. However, most of those studies are conducted on large, general populations rather than on specific populations, such as maritime education learners (Sacurom et al., 2025; Amba & Cacharo, 2025). To sum up, there is a lack of analysis of the relationship between social media and students' study habits in the BSMT education group at DMMA College of Southern Philippines, Inc.

Recent research has revealed a direct relationship between social media and students' study habits, particularly in time management, study routine, and study techniques. Excessive social media usage has been linked to increased procrastination and reduced self-control, which can compromise good study habits (Kircaburun et al., 2018). Social media engagement leads to cognitive distractions that hinder attention and reduce the time students devote to studying (Masood et al., 2020). Furthermore, excessive use of social media leads to academic underachievement, as social phobia and FOMO (Fear of Missing Out) inhibit study efficiency and motivation (Gong et al., 2025).

This research will extend that knowledge; thus, it should help deliver the findings to the right people in the right way. Some research evidence suggests that a well-planned dissemination strategy is better suited to targeted groups, thereby increasing the likelihood of translating research findings into applied applications (Ashcraft et al., 2020). The knowledge can therefore be transferred to the teachers and administrators of DMMA College of Southern Philippines, Inc., especially in maritime education, and to help make significant decisions and enhance their learning outcomes. At the international level, publication in peer-reviewed open-access journals, as well as presentations at academic conferences, will afford researchers, educators, and practitioners worldwide the opportunity to access the study (Helmer et al., 2023). Moreover, studies have shown that publishing results in alternative formats or across multiple venues makes it easier to share findings with diverse audiences, such as students, faculty, and community members (Hu et al., 2024). Further to this, social media may be an excellent venue for enhancing visibility and dissemination of the research outputs (Roberts-Lewis et al., 2024).

Theoretical Framework

Social Cognitive Theory (SCT), established by Albert Bandura, perceives behavior as a product of interactions among cognitive factors, behavioral patterns, and environmental influences. In this study, social media platforms such as Facebook and Twitter / Threads are treated as contextual factors that promote students' intellectual and study behaviors (Nickerson, 2023). Perez et al. (2023) noted that digital social environments shape how learners make sense of information and regulate their academic behaviors. Also, Al-Rahmi et al. (2022) proposed that students' learning outcomes are influenced by their social media through cognitive engagement and self-regulated learning. Chou et al. (2024) found that cognition is one of the central factors influencing behavioral responses in online learning contexts. Thus, all of these perspectives provide a solid theoretical basis for investigating the relationship between social media and study habits of BSMT students.

Furthermore, based on Social Cognitive Theory, a wide array of constructs, such as observational learning, self-regulation, and reciprocal determinism, is also relevant to the variables considered in this research. Lin et al. (2024) stated that students perceived self-efficacy and self-regulated learning strategies have a significant impact on study methods and academic engagement. Online environments can be either useful or restrictive for students' time management, study routines, and study techniques, depending on how students use digital platforms (Kara et al., 2024). Hartley et al. (2020) noted that technology use has a strong effect on self-regulated learning, which, in turn, is correlated with academic performance. These principles help identify how certain domains of social media can play a significant role in predicting the study habits of BSMT students and complement the framework of the existing study.

Conceptual Framework

Figure 1 presents the study variables. The independent variable is social media, specifically Facebook and Twitter/Threads, among maritime students of DMMA College of Southern Philippines, Inc. social media refers to the frequency and manner in which students engage with online platforms for communication, information sharing, and social interaction. Tafesse (2022) stated that higher levels of activity on social networking websites can reduce the time students allocate to academic tasks and lead to distraction. Likewise, excessive social media can adversely affect students' academic behaviors if not properly regulated (Bhandarkar, 2021).

The dependent variable is study habits, defined as time management, study routines, and study techniques. Study habits are the procedures and habits that students follow to organize and complete their academic obligations. Nagaraju et al. (2024) reported that students' social media habits significantly influence their study habits, which, in turn, affect their academic performance. In addition, Nnaji et al. (2020) describe how inconsistent study routines and poor time management are associated with poor social media regulation. These findings support the assumption that social media significantly affects the study habits of BSMT students.

Figure 1. *Conceptual Framework Showing the Variables of the Study*

Statement of the Problem

This study investigates the relationship between social media and study habits among BSMT students at DMMA College of Southern Philippines, Inc. During the second semester, S.Y. 2025 – 2026. It specifically aims to address the following questions:

1. What is the level of social media among BSMT students in terms of:
 - 1.1 Facebook; and,
 - 1.2 Twitter/Threads?
2. What is the level of study habits among BSMT students in terms of:
 - 2.1 Time Management;
 - 2.2 Study Routines; and,
 - 2.3 Study Techniques?
3. Is there a significant relationship between social media and the study habits of BSMT students?
4. What domains of social media significantly influence the study habits of the BSMT students?

Literature Review

This subsection presents the applicable reading materials in the study, organized by social media and study habits, and aligned with the studied variables. Amin et al. (2016) define social media, such as Facebook and Twitter/Threads, as tools that can affect students' attention, time allocation, and attentional focus on school tasks. Palad and Flores (2025) measure study habits in terms of time management, study routine, and study techniques; thus, these are good indicators. Time management is mostly about scheduling and moderating hours of study; study routines: how often students adhere to a regular timetable; and study techniques: note-taking, reviewing lessons, and organizing materials. The following indications form the basis for the authors' exploration of the association between social media and study habits of BSMT students, based on this study.

Social Media

Social media is a system of communicating, socializing, and sharing information online, among which, for students, Facebook and Twitter/Threads are among the most popular. Valdez et al. (2020) reported that social media offers academic benefits through access to subject data and learning, but it can have a harmful impact when consumed in excess, making learning more difficult. Furthermore, the study by Shafiq and Parveen (2023) indicates that more frequent social media use among higher education students may be associated with poorer academic performance, reduced participation in academic tasks, and a lack of sustained long-term focus. Farouk and Jaafar (2025) argued that social media can disrupt students' study periods and their concentration while learning. In addition, according to Abigail and Arowolo (2025), intense use of social media may disturb study habits and alter study behavior.

Furthermore, recent research suggests that the influence of social media on students' study behavior depends primarily on how and why it is used. Al-Rahmi et al. (2022) argued that sharing learning experiences and mutual assistance among peers through social media can enhance student involvement and learning outcomes. When, on the contrary, students tend to overuse non-academic tasks on devices during academic seasons, and suffer from decreased attention, increased multitasking, and weakened self-discipline (Ophir et al., 2009). In a related study, Karpinski et al. (2013) found that academic work interspersed with social networking leads to shorter attention spans and ineffective study methods among students. These findings further indicate that, although important tools for education, social media may also challenge the development of successful study, making it particularly significant to investigate the balance between academic and personal use of social media among maritime students at present. Collectively, these studies set a baseline for assessing whether Facebook and Twitter/Threads may influence the study habits

of BSMT students, and the need to identify both the good and bad aspects of social media in scholarly society.

Facebook

Yotyodying et al. (2021) noted that when implemented for learning purposes, especially in communication, collaboration, and resource sharing, programs can promote that type of learning. Bou Hamad et al. (2020) stated that social media, especially Facebook, is associated with poor academic performance because it competes with study time and distracts students from their academic work. Sakhieva et al. (2024) also observed that heavy social media reduces academic concentration and time devoted to studying. Thus, the amount of Facebook usage affects the study habits and impacts students' performance and engagement.

Moreover, previous academic literature has demonstrated the impact of Facebook use on students' sustained attention in relation to their studies and time management. Meier and Reinecke (2020) stated that Facebook use has led to habitual checking behavior and interruptions during sustained study periods, reducing learning efficiency. Correspondingly, Islam et al. (2020) found that excessive Facebook use among university students is associated with reduced sustained attention capacity and poor academic self-discipline. Similarly, Essien (2025) investigated the impact of long-term Facebook use on temporal displacement, attentional fragmentation, and disrupted study routines, leading students to lose commitment to their studies. The study's three empirical findings suggest that unchecked Facebook use may negatively affect students' study habits and academic engagement.

Twitter/Threads

Joseph et al. (2023) found satisfaction with using Twitter as a learning tool, implying that it supports academic interaction without directly improving academic content. The purposeful use of Twitter is crucial, more important than being on time, and leads to improved learning outcomes (Amiruzzaman & Amiruzzaman, 2022). Although Alshehri (2020) found that Twitter use in a flipped classroom does not lead to increased academic achievement, it does increase students' motivation and positive attitudes towards learning. Alshaye et al. (2023) found that Twitter has a bigger impact on student engagement than on academic performance. Thus, Twitter use may affect study habits through motivational factors, engagement in learning, and consistency in learning.

In addition to satisfaction, motivation, and engagement, it has already been found that Twitter and other social networks influence students' learning behavior and study habits. Additionally, research suggests that when students engage with social networking websites with high academic or learning intentions, these sites are viewed as more engaging and that they learn more from them, even though their academic performance does not improve (Van Cuong, 2025; Kircaburun et al., 2024). New reviews of Twitter in the context of learning show that it primarily increases student participation and interaction with classmates and course materials, rather than academic success (Alshaye, 2023). Research on universities' use of social media also indicates that purposeful, organized interaction, such as participating in meaningful discourse or exchanging relevant information, helps students adopt learning behaviors and become more involved in their learning process. Too much unscheduled use, however, can cause distractions that will make studies less efficient and less focused (Chowdhury, 2024). In sum, this research lends support to the argument that Twitter seems to influence study behaviors more by shaping how students are absorbed into and motivated by the activity and how much they persist in engaging academically, rather than by increasing academic success.

Study Habits

Study habits are the planned practices, processes, or habits that students use to manage, organize, plan, and execute a series of activities within a given study and related learning. These are representations of students' use of their time for learning, routine, and action that serve their learning goals. As Palad and

Flores (2025) suggest, study habits encompass time management, study routines, and study techniques, which work together to keep students engaged and learning. Fu et al. (2025) reported that students who effectively utilize their study time are more concentrated and productive. Dagoc and Oco (2024) also reported that students who study regularly with consistent, organized review schedules are likely to experience increased academic performance and persistence. Furthermore, Fu et al. (2025) noted that study habits, when aligned with self-regulated learning practices such as goal setting, planning, and organizing materials, enhanced academic performance and sustained attention during learning events.

The basis for effective study is primarily motivational orientation and cognitive strategies, which influence the study mode. There is evidence that students with an organized learning strategy and a dynamic approach to studying tend to retain their learning and achieve good grades (Sahito, 2025). When adequately incorporated into study schedules, digital media and academic tools can support a more organized, time-efficient, and high-student-engagement approach to reducing attentional clutter (Faza, 2025). Lastly, practicing study habits over time leads to improved self-monitoring and a more effective approach to tough academic tasks (Suleiman, 2024), underscoring the close association between consistency in study practices and learning strategies and sustained success in these fields.

Time Management

Valente et al. (2024) found that students who schedule study periods are less likely to procrastinate and are much more likely to improve their academic progress steadily. Kanwal et al. (2024) indicated that students who develop self-regulated time-management habits have better organizational skills and focus, facilitating better academic work management. Regular study time is strongly associated with academic achievement as students become increasingly organized and efficient (Ghafar, 2023).

Zuo et al. (2025) also reported that future-focused daily time management behaviors are associated with better academic performance and more consistent task completion. In the same vein, Lourenço and Paiva (2024) found that academic time planning promotes self-regulation and continued attention when completing school assignments, while purposeful examination of study hours is found to be a deterrent against procrastination, increasing the quality and consistency of schoolwork according to Khanam et al. (2017), all these findings collectively support the idea that time management is an essential component of study habits that helps students to be disciplined, manage their time well, perform strongly in their studies, and even avoid procrastination altogether.

Study Routines

Dagoc & Oco (2024) discuss routine study behaviors concerning time-consistent academic review, literature review, and note-taking that lead to systematic access to relevant academic materials and, consequently, academic success. Additionally, when researchers establish consistent study habits correlated with general academic success, this is often due to familiar study behaviors (Zaidi, 2023). Khatun et al. (2025) noted that organizing their study plans around scheduled study patterns enables students to better manage their study schedules, workloads, and retention. The quality, discipline, task control, and learning that learners receive should then depend on the types of study practices they engage in.

Adhering to good study habits will help students organize their work, earn better grades, and improve their academic performance. Likewise, Omoniyi and Fawehinmi (2025) demonstrated that students who follow study routines and schedule study sessions perform better than those who do not. These findings demonstrate the relationships among self-study schedules, the study patterns practiced within them, self-discipline and workload management, and academic performance. Valente et al. (2024) emphasized the significance of routine in studying, as a disciplined approach improves students' retention of information and their grades, suggesting that this systematic strategy becomes part of their regular learning practices in successful studies. These findings demonstrate the relationships among self-study schedules, the study patterns practiced within them, self-discipline and workload management, and academic performance.

Study Techniques

According to Rinella and Putnam (2022), studying strategies such as self-testing and spaced study helped students achieve long-term learning more effectively than less strategic approaches. Moreover, Serra et al. (2025) reported that retrieval practice, the active recall of information from memory, actually improves comprehension and helps consolidate memory, and is an extremely effective tool for improving academic achievement. Aguilar Altamirano et al. (2024) also noted that methods such as summarizing information, elaboration, and the use of structured tools facilitate meaningful cognitive activity and positively impact student achievement. As such, the quantity of study methods has implications for students' ability to absorb, retain, and retrieve information correctly.

Students used evidence-based strategies (e.g., practice testing, distributed practice, and elaboration) and demonstrated higher metacognition and better academic achievement, as reported by Hazlett (2025). Similarly, according to Aguilar Altamirano et al. (2024), the strategies students employ differently can also develop cognitive abilities, enabling deep learning and critical thinking. Taken together, these studies suggest that multiple evidence-based methods lead to greater information retention, deeper learning, and higher academic achievement.

METHODS

This chapter defines the methods that are used in this study. It provides details on the research design, research locale, research respondents, research instrument, data-gathering procedures, and statistical treatment of the data. These sections outlined the procedures for data collection, organization, and analysis to determine whether there is a relationship between social media and study habits among BSMT students at DMMA College of Southern Philippines, Inc.

Research Design

This study utilized a non-experimental quantitative research design, based on a descriptive-correlational study exploring the interaction between social media and study habits. Given the nature of the study, which involved analyzing the variables under investigation (Creswell, 2023), descriptive-correlational research was justified. This study design allowed the researchers to collect data from participants while they behaved naturally and to analyze the data using statistical techniques such as Pearson's correlation and regression to identify patterns and predictive relationships among variables (Morallas & Baguio, 2025). Social media (Facebook and Twitter/Threads) was the independent variable in this study, while study habits (time management, study routines, study techniques) were the dependent variables. A descriptive-correlational design was appropriate because the variables were measured and analyzed freely, and no manipulation was involved, thereby supporting the study objectives.

Research Locale

This study took place at DMMA College of Southern Philippines, Inc., located along Tigatto Road, Buhangin, Davao City, Region XI, Philippines. DMMA College of Southern Philippines, Inc., an eminent maritime school in Mindanao, provides maritime education and training to develop students into globally competitive maritime workforce professionals. Davao City has been a major educational and economic center in the southern Philippines, with diverse student populations and an increasing use of digital tools and services within the education system (Philippine Statistics Authority [PSA], 2023). With the high exposure to digital platforms and online communication tools among BSMT students, the location was suitable for the study. With those characteristics, they became eligible respondents for a study of the link between social media and study habits. Moreover, higher education institutions in the Philippines continued to evolve into technology-enabled learning environments, thereby shaping students' behaviors and habits

(Commission on Higher Education [CHED], 2022). Due to this, DMMA College of Southern Philippines, Inc. was accordingly regarded as an appropriate setting for this study's variable investigation.

Participants and Sampling Technique

The participants of this study were the Bachelor of Science in Marine Transportation (BSMT) students in the Academic Year 2025–2026, comprising 689 first-year students, 681 second-year students, and 679 third-year students, for a total of 2,049. Given the participants' active involvement in academic responsibilities and regular use of social media, the relationship between social media and study habits can be investigated. For sample size determination, the researchers used Slovin's formula with a 5% margin of error (Taherdoost, 2016), which is commonly used in survey research when the total population is known, and variability is uncertain. From this computation, a sample of 113 first-year, 111 second-year, and 111 third-year students can be computed from the resulting 335 respondents. In addition, the respondents were recruited using a stratified random sampling approach to ensure sufficient representation across each year level, followed by a simple random sample to avoid bias in sample selection, considering given time constraints, accessibility, and available resources for the conduct of the study.

Research Instrument

In this Research, an adapted questionnaire was used to collect primary data. The questionnaire consisted of two sections, aligned with the study variables: social media and study habits. Content validity was established by adapting the questionnaire components, as referenced in published studies, to address the research aims.

Part I looked at social media platforms, specifically Facebook and Twitter/Threads. Many of the indicators used here are also adapted from Amin et al. (2016), who examined the effects of social media on students' academic performance. These comprised eight (8) items to evaluate students' level of engagement, frequency of use, and engagement in academic-related activities, and perceived influence of Facebook and Twitter/Threads on their academic behavior. Part II focused on the study habits such as time management, study routines, and study techniques. As noted earlier, the measures contained in this section were modified from the scale created by Palad and Flores (2025).

This aspect had twenty-four (24) items regarding students' time management, study routines, and study techniques. The questionnaire used a Likert scale from 1 (Strongly Disagree) to 5 (Strongly Agree) to measure each indicator. Before data collection, the questionnaire was validated by a panel of experts to ensure it was understandable in content and information, and that the study had a purpose.

The pilot test was conducted with specific BSMT students who were not part of the actual respondents. Cronbach's alpha was used to assess the instrument's internal consistency. Response was measured using the 5-point Likert scale. Weighted mean scores were therefore estimated and analyzed for the corresponding numerical ranges to assess BSMT students' social media and study habits.

Data Gathering

Data were collected in accordance with respondents' rights, ethically and accurately. To obtain permission to conduct the study, a formal request letter was sent to the Dean of the Maritime Department at DMMA College of Southern Philippines, Inc. Following approval, coordination was established with the course instructors to specify the appropriate period for conducting the survey. Before distributing the questionnaires, researchers informed participants that their participation in the study would be voluntary and their responses would be anonymous and confidential. A signed informed consent form was obtained from all participants to ensure transparency and adherence to ethical principles (Varkey, 2021), including autonomy, confidentiality, and integrity, in research activities.

The questionnaires were then distributed during class hours to ensure clarity and high response rates. Once the survey was complete, questionnaires were collected in real time, and responses were verified

for completeness to reduce missing data. Answers were coded and encoded for subsequent statistical analysis. The data in the original research are organized, documented, and managed accurately and with integrity. Strict adherence to formal survey methodologies and data management practices enhanced data quality and ensured the robustness of the quantitative results (Menon & Muraleedharan, 2020).

Data Analysis

The statistical tools used to analyze the data are: *Mean*. This tool was used to analyze and determine the average score. Questions 1 and 2 assessed social media and study habits among BSMT students. *Standard Deviation*. This tool showed how far the responses deviate from the average. The latter was also assisted with questions 1 and 2. *Pearson r*. This tool was used to examine the relationship between social media and study habits. It was indicated whether the relationship is strong or weak, and whether it was positive or negative. This was a response to question 3. *Multiple Regression Analysis*. This tool was used to identify which social media domain had a significant effect on study habits. This addressed question 4 of the study.

Ethical Consideration

The analysis adhered to ethical standards to protect all personnel involved in the study. Prior to data collection, a formal request was submitted to the authorities of DMMA College of Southern Philippines, Inc., and approval was obtained before the study was conducted. The participants were explained the aims, procedures, and significance of the study in detail. They volunteered willingly to participate in the study, and written informed consent was obtained to provide full knowledge of the study. They were informed that they could also stop at any time without penalty or other consequences.

Confidentiality and anonymity were maintained throughout the study. No identifier data were collected, and all responses were handled with the highest level of privacy. All collected data was for academic use only and handled with integrity and responsibility. Properly managed data was stored, organized, controlled, and accessed to prevent misuse or disclosure. And then the researchers, in an attempt to maintain a positive tone for the study, proved the authenticity and quality of this work by ensuring the data were recorded correctly and reported accurately. The above-mentioned were undertaken to ensure the research was conducted in the most respectful, proper, and ethical manner.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This chapter analyzed the study's results by gathering respondents' responses on social media and study habits among BSMT students at DMMA College of Southern Philippines, Inc. The results are grouped according to the sequence of the research questions: the level of social media, the level of study habits, the correlation between measures, and the regression analysis of social media and study habits.

Table 1. *Level of Students' Social Media*

Indicators	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Facebook	3.95	0.74	High
Twitter/Threads	2.82	1.22	Moderate
Total	3.38	0.83	Moderate

Level of Students' Social Media

Table 1 shows students' social media levels. The mean overall score for students' social media is 3.38, interpreted as moderate, with a standard deviation of 0.83. This shows that respondents sometimes use social media. More precisely, the mean ratings indicate that Facebook received a mean score of 3.95 (standard deviation 0.74), which is high, and Twitter/Threads received a mean score of 2.82 (standard deviation 1.22), which is moderate.

Importantly, BSMT students have moderate levels of social media on average, indicating that it is prevalent in their academic and personal lives. So that students do not just use social media but, in fact, utilize social networks, and balance it with their academic life. A moderate degree of engagement, in addition to providing students with a balance between social media and study, does not overwhelm their study process and gives them space to do their homework. Valdez et al. (2020) emphasized the potential of social media to positively contribute to student academic success when implemented effectively, even in the context of information retrieval and learning improvement. Similarly, Al-Rahmi et al. (2022) concluded that social media, as an academic tool, enhances students' engagement and further cooperation.

Moreover, the results indicate that the effect of social media depends on students' usage. With intentional use, it will perform better for communication and knowledge transfer, while its heavier or less controlled use will negatively impact them during study time, reducing attention and focus. This was revealed by Shafiq and Parveen (2023), who found that the use of social media can reduce academic engagement, and by Farouk and Jaafar (2025), who found that it can affect sustained attention. Additionally, Abigail and Arowolo (2025) note that excessive use can alter study behavior.

Consistent with this concept, Ophir et al. (2009) found that multimedia multitasking impairs attentional control. Karpinski et al. (2013) noted that the simultaneous use of social networking while completing academic tasks correlates with a shortened attention span and poor study habits. The above findings indicate that moderate status denotes equal academic benefits through social media, with consequences that need to be regulated to prevent negative outcomes. As a corollary, the higher student use of Facebook versus Twitter/Threads indicates that Facebook is most available to students for communication, cooperation, and accessing academic materials. They share academic information in small groups with other students, communicate and network outside their classroom on Facebook to support collaboration amongst learning partners, and engage in learning tasks. Yotyodying et al. (2021) noted that because Facebook promotes communication and information sharing with peers, it enhances student learning. That means using Facebook as an effective communication tool to inform students, socialize, or even stimulate learning.

Additionally, students' use of Facebook to facilitate academic activities is consistent with the findings. According to Meier and Reinecke (2020), frequent, habitual check-ins can interfere with sustained attention and reduce learning efficiency. Similarly, Islam et al. (2020) explained that overuse can be detrimental to academic self-discipline and decrease attention span, leading to more struggles to focus on academic studies. Essien (2025) noted that continued use can interfere with study routines and reduce willingness to study.

In line with this, BouHamad et al. (2020) argued that Facebook can compete with study time, whereas Sakhieva et al. (2024) showed that excessive use can negatively affect focus, concentration, and study time. Despite the possible hazards above, constant high usage of Facebook shows that this is a very important platform that is used in a significant way, as it keeps students communicating, getting involved with educational activities, and making them stay connected, making it a more influential platform than the rest of the social media networks.

On the other hand, the low use of Twitter/Threads (compared to Facebook) indicates that it is less favored and used less in students' academic studies. This seems to indicate that students rely on it for seeking and discussing information, but it plays a marginal part in organized learning within an academy. Joseph et al. (2023) discovered that Twitter promotes academic interaction, as students have a platform to share ideas and information. Additionally, Alshehri (2020) demonstrated improvements in students' motivation levels and positive attitudes toward learning, whereas Alshaye et al. (2023) highlighted that its impact was greater on engagement than on direct academic performance.

Moreover, the research results indicate that Twitter/Threads promotes student learning by fostering interaction and exposing students to their learning experiences, rather than academic activities. Amiruzzaman and Amiruzzaman (2022) have reported that learning outcomes are meaningful when the

medium is used with explicit academic intent. Likewise, Van Cuong (2025) and Kircaburun et al. (2024) noted higher academic engagement among students who use social media. Nonetheless, unstructured use may still lead to distractions when not well regulated (Chowdhury, 2024). Thus, Twitter/Threads' level is moderate, suggesting that the academic world is less supportive of students than Facebook.

Level of Students' Study Habits

Table 2 shows the level of student study habits. This indicates that the mean study habits score is 4.14, which is interpreted as high, and that the corresponding SD is 0.56, as most of these are frequently reported among the respondents. Notably, among the indicators, time management received a mean of 4.24 (a very high score) with a standard deviation of 0.58, study routines had a mean of 4.04 (a high score) and a standard deviation of 0.64, and study techniques had a mean of 4.13 (a high score) and a standard deviation of 0.70.

Table 2. *Level of Students' Study Habits*

Indicators	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Time Management	4.24	0.58	Very High
Study Routines	4.04	0.64	High
Study Techniques	4.13	0.70	High
Total	4.14	0.56	High

The results indicate that study habits are high among BSMT students, indicating continuous use of effective study routines in their academic behavior. This means that students have learned structured, ordered study techniques that substantially impact their academic achievement. According to Palad and Flores (2025), study habits are systematic behaviors, such as planning, organizing, and using strategies to facilitate learning. A high level of study habits indicates that students not only complete academic tasks but also do so purposefully and systematically. It is also indicative of self-regulated learning, in which students have control over the learning environment, distractions, and how to adjust their learning strategies to meet their needs. Therefore, students tend to become self-reliant learners and are effective in overcoming the challenges of studying and performing fairly consistently over time.

Moreover, the consistently high quality of study habits suggests students' excellent perseverance, strong focus regulation, strong adherence to discipline, and the ability to adapt to academic obligations. Fu et al. (2025) suggested that students with good study habits tend to be more productive and attentive, while Dagoc and Oco (2024) suggested that students who manage their study routines positively tend to be more effective. They also stated that organized and regular study routines improve their academic performance and persistence. Simultaneously, Sahito (2025) reported that students who use systematic learning practices have greater retention and better achievement in memorizing information and outcomes.

Additionally, Faza (2025) reiterates that using structured study techniques and academic tools facilitates organized, effective learning by reducing distractions and improving work management. In a similar vein, Suleiman (2024) noted that consistent study habits are directly correlated with high self-monitoring capacity, enabling pupils to self-assess their achievements, adapt their methods, and make necessary changes when they encounter challenges in practice. In this way, not only are the students studying effectively, but their continual improvement in how they learn also increases their academic and long-term learning capabilities.

Time management, which achieved the highest overall mean across all indicators, indicates that students are very effective at organizing and allocating their time. This indicates that they can make choices, maintain a pattern, and avoid procrastinating. Good time management enables students to share their work, which helps them meet deadlines and balance academic responsibilities with other commitments. Valente et al. (2024) emphasized that students who plan their study time are more likely to perform better academically. In contrast, Kanwal et al. (2024) emphasized that self-regulatory time management improves

organization, focus, and productivity. That students recognize their academic obligations and actively manage them.

Additionally, good time management is a strong indicator of student success and helps maintain consistency, discipline, and planning in their future work and in how they do it. Regular study hours improve academic performance, and students should adopt consistent learning strategies (Ghafar, 2023). Zuo et al. (2025) also reported that time management is linked with better task completion and less procrastination. In contrast, Lourenço and Paiva (2024) also highlighted proper academic planning as a driver of sustained attention and continued participation in learning tasks in a student-directed direction. In addition, Khanam et al. (2017) noted that examining and optimizing study time facilitates higher-quality academic task work and helps avoid procrastination during task execution. The results show that students' study habits are founded on time management, which directly affects their productivity, reliability, and ability to meet academic goals.

Conversely, study routines, which remained relatively better than the others, registered the smallest average across indicators, indicating that consistency in daily study techniques or study schedule is slightly less important than time management and study techniques. This suggests that students follow a consistent pattern, indicating they engage in study practices; however, when it comes to structured study, they may not have fixed or consistent study plans. The types of study routines include repeating learning events that follow a systematic structure, such as reviewing lessons, organizing notes, and maintaining consistent study patterns. As Dagoc and Oco (2024) stated, consistent study routines improve academic performance, while Zaidi (2023) noted that repetitive learning behaviors help learners remember and grasp material more effectively, thereby improving comprehension over time.

Furthermore, students might value the flexibility of their study routine over an inflexible one, as indicated by the slightly lower score for study routines. Flexibility can be a potential asset in addressing a range of learning styles for students, but inconsistency may at times impact retention and continuity. Khatun et al. (2025) noted that well-structured study routines help students overcome workload, leading to increased retention, while Omoniyi and Fawehinmi (2025) stated that students who follow regular study patterns perform better academically. Valente et al. (2024) also highlighted that discipline in study routines enhances memory retention and academic achievement. These findings indicated that, despite study routines being the least highly valued among the indicators, improvements in consistency in this domain may enhance students' overall learning effectiveness and academic performance.

On the other hand, the study techniques showed a high level, suggesting that students use effective learning strategies fairly often to facilitate their comprehension and retention of information. It indicates that students are engaging in studying through a variety of effective processes, including reviewing, summarizing, organizing information, and practicing recall. Good study techniques help students delve into information, making learning more powerful and permanent. These include self-testing and spaced practice of self-strategies, which significantly improve long-term retention (Rinella & Putnam, 2022). In contrast, Serra et al. (2025) found that retrieval practice can also strengthen comprehension and reinforce memory consolidation.

Moreover, the implementation of study techniques evidences students' ability to think at higher levels while learning and to engage in higher cognitive processes. Aguilar Altamirano et al. (2024) noted that elaboration and summarization techniques make information more meaningful by linking new information to prior knowledge. As Hazlett (2025) showed, students who use evidence-based approaches perform better academically, whereas Aguilar Altamirano et al. (2024) argued that strategic learning styles enhance critical thinking and problem-solving abilities.

Correlation Between Measures

Table 3. *Correlation between Social Media and Study Habits*

	r	p	Decision	Interpretation
Social media and Study Habits	.449	.000	Reject Ho	Significant

Note: Significant at $p < .01$

The correlation between social media and study habits is presented in Table 3. Shapiro-Wilk test was applied to examine the normality of the data and the results were statistically significant ($W = 0.946$, $p < .001$; $W = 0.948$, $p < .001$; and $W = 0.970$, $p < .001$), which represent non-normality distributions, but we used the Pearson r relationship, which is consistent with the $N = 335$ sufficient sample size to satisfy the central limit theorem, making it suitable to use parametric procedures. Social media use is closely linked to study habits. An r -value of .449 shows a moderate relationship. This indicates that the study performs better with more social media.

The computed r -value of .449 suggests that study habits improve as students use social media more. For instance, the number of daily habits students develop that are more positively impacted by using social media platforms also improves. Al-Rahmi et al. (2022) observed that when social media platforms are applied to educational practices, they benefit student and academic engagement. Similarly, Yotyodying et al. (2021) contend that the use of social media fosters collaboration and the sharing of educational content, thereby shaping students' educational habits.

The moderate relationship indicates that social media may influence the formation of study habits, but does not solely influence students' academic behavior. This implies that how well students use social media affects, or even causes harm, in how they use it. By utilizing social media purposefully for academic purposes, Amiruzzaman and Amiruzzaman (2022) noted that "learning outcomes come from a meaningful connection to social media users. In contrast, Van Cuong (2023) found that students who use social media for educational purposes are more academically engaged. Furthermore, Alshaye et al. (2023) found that social media largely contributes to students' participation and motivation, thereby indirectly fostering the practice of good study. These findings suggest that social media can support students' study habits as a supportive mechanism, especially when used strategically and purposefully.

Regression Analysis of Social Media and Study Habits

Table 4 presents the regression analysis of social media domains on BSMT students' study habits. The social media markers Facebook and Twitter/Threads demonstrated a significant influence on students' study habits. The assumptions required for multiple linear regression were examined prior to conducting the analysis. The findings confirmed that the assumptions of linearity, independence of errors, absence of multicollinearity, and normality of residuals were met, and multiple linear regression was suitable for evaluating the predictive relationship between Facebook and Twitter/Threads use and students' study habits ($N = 335$).

Table 4. *Domains of Social Media Influencing Study Habits*

	β	p	Decision	Interpretation
(Constant)	2.986	.000	Reject Ho	Significant
Facebook	0.200	.000	Reject Ho	Significant
Twitter	0.128	.000	Reject Ho	Significant

Note: Model fit at $p=.000$; $r=.453$; $r^2=.205$

The computed R^2 value is .205, indicating that social media domains account for 20.5% of the variance in students' study habits. This also means that 79.5% of the variance is explained by other factors, such as personal motivation, the learning environment, and other academic-related variables, which were not examined in this study. Model fit yielded a p -value of .000, which is below the 0.05 level of significance set in this study, indicating that social media domains significantly affect students' study habits. Therefore,

the null hypothesis is rejected. This proves social media has a significant influence on students' study behavior, especially when used in an academic setting.

The key aim of this study is to identify the social media domain that most strongly predicts students' study habits. Facebook is one of the best social media predictors, whereas Twitter/Threads are weaker predictors; Facebook is a stronger predictor than Twitter/Threads ($\beta = 0.200$ vs. $\beta = 0.128$). Because students learn best when interacting with others, many academic studies developed through group discussion, sharing materials, and communication take place on Facebook. Unlike Twitter/Threads, where we also see notable contributions but with a lower beta, there is less direct influence, as well, supporting engagement but not academic behavior.

The result supports Al-Rahmi et al. (2022), who emphasize academic engagement and interaction on social media for educational purposes. Similarly, Valdez et al. (2020) stated that social media supports learning by connecting academic information with students and promoting academic dialogue. Furthermore, Yotyodying et al. (2022) emphasized that Facebook promotes mutual collaboration and knowledge sharing, which positively influences students to adopt different academic behaviors and study approaches. Instead, the reduced predictive power of Twitter/Threads is consistent with that reported by Alshaye et al. (2023), who found that Twitter overall enhances student participation and motivation but does not increase academic achievement. While both media positively impact students' study, their statistics indicate that Facebook has a more direct, stronger effect on students' academic behaviors.

CONCLUSION

The BSMT students have moderate social media engagement, meaning they sometimes use it in their daily lives. This indicates that although students use social media, they maintain a healthy balance in their online presence and have a strong academic routine.

As for study habits, results indicate that BSMT students in this group are likely to possess a high level, typically achieved through effective time management, good study routines, and study techniques demonstrated on an ongoing basis. This suggests that students' habitual use of structured, systematic learning strategies enables them to manage their academic workload in a timely manner, thereby achieving the goal of learning success. Further, well-formed study routines were said to reflect a high level of discipline and responsibility, both of which are fundamental for academic success.

Moreover, the relationship between social media and study habits was high and significant. And, the more social media students are on (especially for academic purposes), the better they're using academic-related media, meaning that social media is a potential add-on to studying.

Lastly, Facebook and Twitter/Threads are major influences on students' study habits, with Facebook being the most dominant. It argues that what social media platforms do in students' academic behavior is largely dictated by their use. These results also show that social media significantly promotes better use of study time and enhances academic abilities among students with a strong demand for socially responsible, purposeful deeds grounded in academic dimensions.

Recommendations

Based on the results of the study, the following recommendations are:

1. The students are recommended to have more conscious and intentional use of social networking platforms, particularly for academic functions. In addition, they should strive to take control of their online time management so that, when they are on social media, their use does not interfere with academic work but rather enhances it.
2. The students' study habits need to be reinforced, including time management, study routines, and study techniques—they should continue to adopt study schedules and learning strategies. They are

also advised to use social media academically to improve their learning quality and academic performance further.

3. The teachers are advised to use social media sites (specifically Facebook & Twitter/Threads) for interactive and collaborative learning to improve students' learning. They could establish online academic groups, share learning materials, and help students use social media for educational engagement to improve their study habits further.
4. The school administrators should promote the use of technology and social media in the learning environment with guidance, training, and programs that promote academic use of social media using appropriate methods.
5. The policymakers must formulate policies and frameworks. These policies should be intended to ensure that social media is as effective as possible for academic learning and as minimally distracting as possible, so students can maximize their learning when using it.
6. Future researchers must take other variables into consideration in studying habits, such as motivation, learning environment, and technological skills. They could also consider other research designs or expand the study to include more academic programs or higher education institutions to confirm their conclusions.

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